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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AADITH SUGEEESH bearing USN 6SU20FS001 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIRAM T bearing USN 6SU20FS002 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEN BENNY bearing USN 6SU20FS003 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANGEL N J bearing USN 6SU20FS004 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYA CHANDRAN bearing USN 6SU20FS005 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWATHY PRAKASH bearing USN 6SU20FS006 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BIMAL S G bearing USN 6SU20FS007 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHANDANA P bearing USN 6SU20FS008 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DELMA DSOUZA bearing USN 6SU20FS009 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVIKA P S bearing USN 6SU20FS010 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOKUL RAJ K K bearing USN 6SU20FS011 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOPIKA P bearing USN 6SU20FS012 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JESLIN GEORGE T N bearing USN 6SU20FS013 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIKA M GOPI bearing USN 6SU20FS014 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LAVANYA T bearing USN 6SU20FS015 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEGHANA G BHAT bearing USN 6SU20FS016 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED THANVEER M P bearing USN 6SU20FS017 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAJMA P A bearing USN 6SU20FS018 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIRANJANA P P bearing USN 6SU20FS019 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PUNYA JAYACHANDRAN bearing USN 6SU20FS020 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAJ KRISHNAN R bearing USN 6SU20FS021 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANLEAO MATHEW bearing USN 6SU20FS022 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SOORYA K bearing USN 6SU20FS023 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VAIBHAV SANTHOSH bearing USN 6SU20FS024 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU R bearing USN 6SU20FS025 has completed his/her internship at Crime branch Bureau Kasargod in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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